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Impact of Fluazifop-p-butyl Exposure on Transferases and Phosphatase in *Clarias gariiepinus*

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Impact of Fluazifop-p-butyl Exposure on Transferases and Phosphatase in *Clarias gariepinus*

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ABSTRACT

Careless use of pesticide poses animal and human health concerns globally. Pesticide can find their way into food chain, hence the need to examine the effect of fluazifop-P-butyl in *Clarias gariepinus*. *Clarias gariepinus* (mean length, 16.04±0.23cm, mean weight 94.05±0.60) were acclimatized to laboratory conditions for seven days and then exposed to varying concentrations of fluazifop-p-butyl in static bioassay for 30 days. Alanine amino transferase (ALT), aspartate amino transferase (AST), and Alkaline transferase (ALP), were evaluated in the liver and plasma. A significant decline was observed in ALT and ALP values in the liver. A slight increase was also observed in plasma ALT. AST values were significant in the liver akin to plasma, ALP showed a progressive elevation in the experimental group. The study concluded that fluazifop-p-butyl may be toxic at high concentration. Enzymes are more valuable biomarkers of sublethal effect of this toxicant in non-target organisms in the aquatic environment.

Keywords: Fluazifop-p-butyl, *Clarias gariepinus*, phosphatasees, transferases.

INTRODUCTION

Public awareness about the negative effects of pesticides on aquatic organisms and bioaccumulation in fish and other aquatic organisms are fast increasing (Izah and Angaye, 2016). Herbicides which are applied on agricultural land and other anthropogenic uses, up to 90% of this never reach the intended targets (Sparling et al., 2001). As a result, many other non target organisms sharing the same environment are unintentionally poisoned (Inyang et al., 2016a-e, 2017). World health organization estimated that 3 million incidence of pesticide poisoning occurs annually and it lead to over 250,000 deaths (Yang and Den, 2007).

Fluazifop-p-butyl is a post emergence phenoxy herbicide (Inyang et al., 2016a,b). It is absorbed rapidly through leaf surfaces and quickly hydrolysis to fluazifop acid (Inyang et al., 2016a,b). The acid it contains is mainly transported via the phloem and it accumulates in the meristems where it have adverse effect (i.e. disrupts the synthesis of lipids in susceptible species) (Urano, 1982., Balinora and Lalora, 1992). Fluazifop-p-butyl inhibits acetyl Co-A carboxylase, an enzyme that catalysis an early step in fatty acid synthesis (Inyang et al., 2016a,b). Lipids are vital components of cellular membranes, and when they cannot be produced in sufficient quantities, cell membrane integrity fails, especially in the regions of active growth. This could lead to burst, or leakage of even death of the cell (Exttoxnet, 1996).

Uncritical pesticides use in the environment coupled with accidental discharge of untreated effluent into natural waterways have harmful effects on fisheries population and other forms of aquatic life and contribute to long term effects in the environment (Rahman et al., 2002; Izah and Angaye, 2016).

Fish species however, are most sensitive to aquatic pollutants during their early life states (Jiruangoorskul et al., 2002). Pesticides at high concentration lead to decline in growth and reproduction in fisheries, leading to several adverse effects on fisheries. Additionally, due to the residual effects of chemical, important organs in fish are damaged (Rahman et al., 2002).

Fishes are suitable indicators for assessing the effect of contaminants/toxicant on the environment. This is because they can bioaccumulate and biomagnify contaminants from its environment and/ or diet at various tissues/organ (Larfranchi et al., 2006; Izah and Angaye, 2016). Low activity of the mono-oxygenase enzymes in fishes restrictions their capability to metabolize some pesticides eg Organochlorines (Sarkar et al., 2008). These have resulted to the study of effect environmental contaminants and the bioaccumulation of pollutants by biodiversity found in the aquatic ecosystem (Sarkar et al., 2008; Izah and Angaye, 2016).

Evaluation of enzymes activities in the tissue and organs of aquatic organisms in the diagnosis of the effects of pollutants is one of the emerging areas in toxicological monitoring and remediation (Oluah et al., 2005). Enzyme

Activity is one major parameter used in assessing the early stage of pesticide toxicity (Duta and Areids, 2003). There are several reports of enzyme aberrations in organs and blood of organisms as a result pesticide (Svodova et al., 2001., Velisek et al., 2006, Inyang, 2008, Inyang, 2014. Nagat and Kawther, 2015).

The objective of this work was to study the effect of fluazifop-p-butyl on biochemical parameters in *Clarias gariepinus* (a common, Niger Delta wetland fish). The goal was to access an effect of fluazifop-p-butyl on *Clarias gariepinus* (a widely cultured fish in Nigeria) on some biochemical parameters in fish (*Clarias gariepinus*). These parameters and organs tested are chosen because of the vital role they play in the probe organism's metabolism and general physiology. The toxic effect of the toxicant was assessed based on the result of chronic toxicity tested after the exposure to the herbicide.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experimental stock

Fish samples for this study were obtained from Biotechnology resource centre, Odi, Bayelsa State. They were transported to the Department Fisheries and Animal Science, Niger Delta University, Wilberforce Island, Bayelsa State, Nigeria, where the assays were conducted. Thirty (30) healthy adult *Clarias gariepinus* with mean weight $94.05 \pm 0.6g$, and mean length $16.04 \pm 0.23cm$ were acclimated individually in a rectangular aquaria for seven days during which they were fed once a day (9.00 – 11.00hours) with 35% crude protein diet at 1% biomass.

Test chemical

Sublethal concentration of fluazifop-p-butyl for the assay (0.01, 0.02, and 0.03ppm) was determined based on the range finding test (Inyang, 2008). These were prepared by transferring 0.002, 0.004 and 0.006mls respectively from original concentration (150g/l) of the toxicant and making it up to 30L with borehole water in the test aquaria, 30L of the diluent was used as control.

General bioassay technique

Four bioassay of each treated level (concentrations) and control were set up by introducing fishes individually into each aquarium. The exposed period lasted 30 days during which the exposed media were renewed every 48hours. The physiochemical characterization of the water used for fish bioassay was carried out using standard methods (APHA, 1998) and the values obtained ranged from 24.05 – 24.20 °C (Temperature), 6.15 – 6.24 (pH), (97.43 – 135.02 μ /cm) conductivity, 11.31 – 17.13mg/l (Alkalinity), 5.21 – 7.13mg/l (Dissolved oxygen), and 0.13 – 0.46NTU (turbidity).

The activity of aspartate amino transferase (AST and alanine amino transferase (ALT) were assayed using the colorimetric method of Reitman and Fronkel (1957) while alkaline phosphatase was assayed via Halkenchied and Kohler (1986).

Statistical analysis

The data were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA). Where differences exist, Duncan multiple range test (DMRT) were used to test for pair wise significant differences ($P < 0.05$) between treatments (Wahua, 1999).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Enzymes in the liver

A significant ($P < 0.05$) decline was observed in ALT in the liver. The control recorded $137.00 \pm 11.10\mu/l$ while the highest concentration of the toxicant recorded $55.30 \pm 0.06 \mu/l$. the reduction was dose dependent akin to ALP except at 0.01ppm. AST values was recorded in all the experimental concentrations. The highest value was recorded at 0.02ppm (Table 1).

ALT and AST are enzymes involved in the catabolism of amino acids. The measurement of serum or plasma levels of these enzymes is a standard feature of clinical chemistry. According Hall (2001), probable causes of decline in serum/plasma activities of ALT and AST include decline in hepatocellular production or release of the enzymes, additionally, inhibition or decline of the enzyme's activity. The reduction in values of AST and ALP may be because interruption in the secretion functions as well as inhibition. It may also be associated to the response of AST to the toxicant in order to detoxify or metabolize the xenobiotic.

Solter et al. (2000) noted that reduction or increased levels of ALT will affect the metabolic abilities of the liver. The authors also speculate that regulation of ALT synthesis could affect the ability of the liver to metabolize amino acids for the production of energy for the cell. They added that this could limit the capacity of the hepatocytes to maintain appropriate energy levels.

Enzymes in the plasma

A slight increase was observed in the plasma ALT as the concentration increased, albeit not statistically significant except at 0.01ppm. A progressive elevation in values of ALP was also recorded as the concentration of the toxicant increased, similar to AST that recorded a significant variation ($P < 0.05$) values as the concentration increased at 0.01 and 0.02ppm (Table 2).

Table 1: Activities of ALT, AST and ALP in liver of *Clarias gariepinus* exposed to Fluazifop-p-butyl for 30 days (mean \pm SD)

Conc of Fluazifop-p-butyl (ppm)	ALT (μ l)	AST(μ l)	ALP(μ l)
0.00	137.00 \pm 11.10 ^a	81.10 \pm 0.99 ^d	109.00 \pm 4.00 ^{ab}
0.01	71.00 \pm 11.10 ^b	191.00 \pm 8.4 ^c	211.50 \pm 3.05 ^a
0.02	60.10 \pm 0.07 ^b	376.50 \pm 7.10 ^a	101.00 \pm 0.98 ^{ab}
0.03	55.30 \pm 0.06 ^c	3.00 \pm 10.10 ^b	93.00 \pm 6.41 ^b

Means with the same superscript within the same column indicate no significant different ($P < 0.05$)

Table 2: Activities of ALT, AST and ALP in plasma of *Clarias gariepinus* exposed to Fluazifop-p-butyl for 30 days (mean \pm SD)

Conc of Fluazifop-p-butyl (ppm)	ALT (μ l)	AST(μ l)	ALP(μ l)
0.00	66.00 \pm 0.12 ^b	267.00 \pm 10.01 ^b	19.50 \pm 1.02 ^b
0.01	102.00 \pm 0.68 ^a	423.00 \pm 10.08 ^a	17.00 \pm 0.09 ^{ab}
0.02	68.50 \pm 1.12 ^b	331.50 \pm 7.11 ^{ab}	20.50 \pm 0.08 ^b
0.03	70.50 \pm 1.08 ^b	240.00 \pm 4.56 ^b	25.30 \pm 0.08 ^a

Means with the same superscript within the same column indicate no significant different ($P < 0.05$)

AST and ALP are basically kidney and liver enzymes and their occurrence in the blood or plasma is an indication of pathological condition which is possible pointer to a damaged or ruptured kidney or liver due to toxic effect of xenobiotics. This present research showed a remarkably effect of fluazifop-p-butyl on *Clarias gariepinus*. The liver AST values declines as the level of the toxicant increased (Table 1). The offshoot of this reduction leads to elevation in plasma ALT and AST (Table 2). This is akin to ALP trend in the liver and plasma. Elevation of values in the plasma

is clear evidence that the toxicant had a profound effect on the liver cells. Similar result was also obtained by Inyang et al. (2013) when they exposed *Clarias gariepinus* to dichlorvos, an organophosphate insecticide. They opined that tissue damage or necrosis resulting from injury or disease is generally accompanied by increase in the levels of several non-functional plasma enzymes.

Alterations in the values of AST, AST and ALP will have consequential effect on the adequate transportation of required ions across the cell membrane, glutathionic metabolism as well as metabolism and regulation of amino acids (Karthikeyan et al., 2006). The elevation of values of these enzymes in the plasma may be associated to the lethal effect of the toxicant on kidney and liver cells, which can lead to alterations in enzymes stability in the probe organism. Our data demonstrated that repeated sublethal doses of fluzifop-pbutyl caused a significant alteration in the level of tested enzymes in the plasma and liver (one the main vital organ of all biochemical processes in the probe organism).

CONCLUSION

The present study demonstrated that excessive exposure to fluzifop-p-butly caused changes in the hepatic biochemical makers. The use of this toxicant near aquatic environment should be carried out with caution.

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